

Comparative Analysis of Intracorporeal vs. Extracorporeal Anastomosis in Minimally Invasive Right Colectomies for Colorectal Cancer

Konstantinos Kossenas^{1*}, Andreas I. Biris¹, Ioannis Karamatzanis¹, Foteini Soukouli¹, Olga Moutzouri¹, Beatrice Catalli², Ifigenia Kokkofiti¹, James Zhang³, Eleni Gkraikou⁴, Marina Blagka Thalassini⁴, Myrofora Demetriou¹, Ioannis Christos Giallelis¹, Ioannis Stefanakis¹, Filippos Georgopoulos⁵

¹Department of Basic Clinical Sciences, University of Nicosia, Nicosia, Cyprus

²Internal Medicine, Università Vita Salute San Raffaele, Milan, Italy

³Department of Orthopedics, Addenbrooke's Hospital, University Hospital NHS Foundation Trust, United Kingdom

⁴Department of Health Sciences, European University Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus

⁵Department of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, Al Zahra Hospital, Dubai, United Arab Emirates

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***Corresponding author:** Dr. Konstantinos Kossenas, Department of Basic Clinical Sciences, University of Nicosia, Nicosia, Cyprus, Tel: +30-6942594997

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Compare the intracorporeal to the extracorporeal anastomosis for right sided colon cancer performed with minimally invasive methods, identify research gaps in the literature, provide future directions and discuss its implication on healthcare professionals.

Methods: PubMed, Google Scholar and MEDLINE were searched to identify RCTs, Systematic reviews and Meta-analysis that directly compared the intracorporeal to the extracorporeal anastomosis, from 2013 to 2024.

Results: The intracorporeal approach was associated with faster bowel function recovery, smaller incision length, shorter duration of hospitalization, lower blood loss, lower postoperative pain and analgesia usage, lower rates of wound and surgical site infections, lower herniation rates, better intestinal perfusion, lower levels of postoperative inflammation markers, reduced rate of parietal abscess and better intestinal perfusion compared to extracorporeal anastomoses. No significant differences were observed regarding the anastomotic leakage, ileus, morbidity and mortality, time to ambulation, nausea, nasogastric tube re-insertion, re-admission rate, re-operation rate, conversion to open surgery, number of harvested lymph nodes and bowel obstruction. However, the intracorporeal approach required longer operative duration and was more expensive, compared to extracorporeal.

Conclusions: The intracorporeal anastomosis is as safe and feasible as the extracorporeal, however more research is needed to investigate long term and patient centered outcomes currently underreported.

Keywords: Extracorporeal Anastomosis; Intracorporeal Anastomosis; Robotic Colectomy; Laparoscopic Colectomy; Colorectal Cancer

INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third most commonly diagnosed cancer and second in cancer-related mortality^[1]. It is associated with smoking, obesity, diet high in salt and low activity levels^[2]. Its presentation can vary, most commonly presents with pain, change in the bowel habits, hematochezia and weight loss^[3]. Surgery, is one of the most common treatments for CRC, with colectomies being a major part of the treatment plan. CRC surgery entails the removal of the cancerous section and rejoining the remaining parts, which is known as anastomosis. In addition, the implementation of minimally invasive approaches (robot and laparoscopy), has revolutionized surgery. It offers benefits

like fewer operative and post-operative complications, shorter duration of hospitalization, less post-operative pain, faster recovery, less immune stress, less scarring, smaller incisions and for some procedures decreased overall costs and operative duration^[4-6].

Two major types of anastomosis have been discussed in the literature, the intracorporeal (IA) and the extracorporeal (EA) anastomosis. The IA, is performed entirely within the abdomen and has been associated with reduced duration of hospitalization, short-term morbidity and possibly faster recovery^[7]. Conversely, EA, requires the bowel section to be extracted from the abdomen. EA has been the mainstay way of anastomosing bowel in CRC surgeries and surgeons are familiar with it. As the surgical landscape is evolving and moving away from open to minimally invasive approaches, the debate of whether the IA or EA offers better outcomes in laparoscopic or robotic right colectomies, has ensued. However, the evidence is still conflicted. This paper aims to perform a (a) comprehensive comparison between the IA and EA in the context of minimally invasive right sided colectomies for CRC and report the outcomes for operative duration, bowel function recovery, duration of hospitalization, rate of anastomotic leakage, rate of ileus, incision length, overall morbidity and mortality, blood loss, postoperative pain and analgesia use, wound and surgical site infections (SSI), herniation and other less commonly reported outcomes. Also, it aims to (b) underline current research gaps in the literature, (c) report on currently recruiting randomized clinical trials (RCT), (d) provide future directions via potential future RCTs that could bridge the gap in the literature and (e) discuss the implications on healthcare professionals and policy makers.

METHODS

A literature search, using related keywords, was performed in PubMed, Google Scholar and MEDLINE to identify RCTs, Systematic reviews and Meta-analysis (SR/MA) that directly compared the IA to the EA, from 2013 to 2024. RCTs and SR/MA were chosen as they convey some of the highest level of evidence in the literature. Observational, retrospective and review studies were excluded. Also studies that reported on the outcomes of either techniques without comparing one to another were excluded too. Lastly, non-English literature, and transverse and left sided colon surgeries were excluded as well. Similarly, ClinicalTrials.gov was searched for related trials. Only RCTS currently recruiting were selected. In total, three articles comparing robotic and seventeen comparing laparoscopic IA to EA, for the treatment of right sided colon cancers were retrieved (Table 1 and Table 2). Lastly, two currently recruiting RCTs were identified (Table 3).

Table 1: Studies comparing IA to EA in Robotic cohorts, arranged chronologically

Author	Type of study	Country	total number of participants	Key findings
Dohrn et al. (2022) ^[8]	RCT	Denmark	89	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No statistically significant differences between the two types of anastomosis regarding post-operative pain, time to ambulation, nausea, duration of hospitalization, time to first flatus/stools, pathophysiological test and pathology. The duration to perform the anastomosis was significantly longer with the intra-corporeal approach (17 vs 13 minutes, P=0.003).
Dohrn et al. (2022) ^[9]	RCT	Denmark	68	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A steeper slope was observed regarding intestinal perfusion in IA compared to EA (6.3 vs. 4.7 AU/sec, P = .048) no significant associations were observed between the two anastomoses technique regarding the TMAX, FMAX, time ration and T1/2MAX.
Liang et al. (2022) ^[10]	SR/MA	China	585	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IA had a significantly longer operative duration compared to EA (weighted mean difference [WMD]: 28.88, 95% CI 13.88-43.89, p = 0.0002), but a shorter time to first flatus (WMD: - 0.57, 95% CI - 0.95 to 0.19, p = 0.003). No statistically significant differences were observed between the two types of anastomosis regarding blood loss, wound herniation,

				complications, length of incision, incisional hernia rate and duration of hospitalization.
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Table 2: Studies comparing IA to EA in the laparoscopic cohorts, arranged chronologically

Author	Type of study	Country	total number of participants	Key findings
Feroci et al. (2013) ^[11]	SR/MA	Italy	425	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The IA was associated with shorter duration of hospitalization, decreased use of analgesics, faster time to bowel movement and first flatus and shorter time to initiate a solid diet. No statistically significant differences were observed between the two approaches regarding operative duration, incision length, nasogastric tube re-introduction, number of harvested lymph nodes, intraoperative complications, non-surgical site complications, mortality rate, intervention, and readmission rate. Non-statistically significant differences were observed between the two approaches regarding surgical site complications, i.e. Ileus, wound infection, anastomotic bleeding and leakage.
Cirocchi et al. (2013) ^[12]	SR/MA	Italy	945	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No statistically significant differences were observed between the two groups regarding anastomotic leakage and mortality rate. Post-operative morbidity was not possible due to high degree of heterogeneity.

Carnuccio et al. (2014) ^[13]	SR/MA	Spain	483	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The IA was associated with quicker bowel recovery, shorter length of hospitalization and better cosmetic results. No significant differences were observed between the two anastomoses regarding anastomotic leakage (OR 0.98; 95% CI 0.30-3.15) and short term overall morbidity (OR 0.68; 95% CI 0.41-1.12).
Vignalli et al., (2016) ^[14]	RCT	Italy	158	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The IA was associated with quicker bowel function recovery ($P = .048$) and lower incidence of postoperative ileus ($P = .05$), but with longer operative duration ($P = 0.04$) and two cases of anastomotic leakage, compared to EA. No significant differences were observed regarding duration of hospitalization ($P = 0.70$) and complication rates ($P = 0.89$).
Wu et al. (2017) ^[15]	SR/MA	China	1957	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The IA was associated with decreased blood loss, smaller incision length, short time to first stool, shorter time to initiate liquid diet and shorter duration of hospitalization. No differences were observed regarding operative duration, conversion to open surgery, intra-operative complications, and number of lymph nodes harvested, time to first flatus, anastomotic leakage, mortality rate, post-operative complications, wound infection, ileus, anastomotic bleeding, hernia and intra-abdominal abscess.

Ricci et al. (2017) ^[16]	SR/MA	Italy	1717	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non statistically significant, results were observed between the two anastomosis techniques regarding anastomotic leakage (3.4% in IA vs. 4.6% in EA) with a risk difference (RD) of -0.01 (95% CI = -0.03 to 0.01; P = 0.120). • The IA group had an overall lower complication and wound infection rate compared to EA (27.6% vs. 38.4%; RD = -0.15; 95% CI = 0.27 to -0.04; P = 0.009, (4.9% vs. 8.9%; RD = -0.52; -0.03; 95% CI = -0.06 to -0.01; P = 0.030, respectively). • IA outperformed EA in terms of time to first oral intake (weighted mean difference (WMD) = -1; 95% CI = -1.59 to -0.41; P < 0.001), length of hospitalization (WMD = -1.13; 95% CI = -1.90 to -0.35; P = 0.004), and incision length (WMD = -26; 95% CI = -38 to -13; P < 0.001). • The rates of incision hernia were lower in the IA group (2.3% vs. 13.7%) with an RD of -0.09 (95% CI = -0.17 to -0.02; P = 0.020). • No significant differences were observed in operative duration, blood loss, internal hernia, conversion rate, mortality, reoperation rate, time to first flatus and defecation, number of harvested lymph nodes, length of distal resection margin and analgesic requirements.
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Mari et al. (2018) ^[17]	RCT	Italy	60	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interleukin-6 and C-reactive protein were significantly lower in the IA group on post-operative days 1, 3 and 5 compared to EA. • Bowel function recovery occurred much earlier in the IA group compared to the EA.
Allaix et al. (2019) ^[18]	RCT	Italy	140	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No significant differences were observed regarding the operative duration, duration of hospitalization, number of lymph nodes harvested, incision length, reoperation rates, 30-day morbidity rates and readmission rate. • No intraoperative complications were reported for either techniques.
Aiolfi et al. (2020) ^[19]	SR/MA	Italy	3755	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the IA had a lower postoperative infectious complications ratio [0.51 (95% CI: 0.31 to 0.84; P = .009)], lower overall complication risk ratio [0.78 (95% CI: 0.62 to 0.97; P = .028)], quicker time to first flatus [-16.68 (P < .001)], earlier initiation of oral diet [-16.35 (P < .001)], quicker first defecation [-25.94 (P < .001)] and shorter hospitalization length [-0.72 (P < .001)] compared to EA. • No significant differences were observed between the two types of anastomoses regarding anastomotic leakage, operative duration, reoperation rate, ileus, conversion rate, bleeding, 30-day mortality rate, and 30 day readmission rate.

Selvy et al. (2020) ^[20]	MA	France	3699	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The IA was associated with a decreased risk of parietal abscesses (Odds Ratio [OR] 0.526, Confidence Interval [CI] 0.333-0.832, p = 0.006).
Bollo et al. (2020) ^[21]	RCT	Spain	140	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the IA group had a shorter incision length (median 6.7 vs. 8.7 cm; P < 0.001), faster bowel function recovery (median 2.3 vs. 3.3 days; P = 0.003), lower rates of ileus (13% vs. 30%; P = 0.022), lower rate of postoperative decrease in hemoglobin level (mean 8.8 vs. 17.1 mg/dl; P = 0.001), lower rate of gastrointestinal bleeding (3% vs. 14%; P = 0.031), lower rate of grade I and II complications, lower post-operative analgesic requirements (mean weighted analgesia requirement 39 vs. 53; P = 0.001), lower pain (P = 0.035), compared to EA. The IA group was associated with a longer operative duration (median 149 vs. 123 minutes; P < 0.001).
Zhang et al. (2021) ^[22]	SR/MA	China	559	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the IA group had significantly earlier time to first flatus (MD -0.71, 95% CI -1.12 to -0.31, P = 0.0005), lower pain in the 3rd, 4th and 5th postoperative days using the visual analogue scale, earlier onset of first tool passage (MD -0.53, 95% CI -0.69 to -0.37, P < 0.00001), shorter incision length (MD -1.52, 95% CI -2.30 to -0.74, P = 0.0001), and lower wound infection (relative risk 0.46, 95% CI 0.23 to 0.91, P = 0.02). No statistically significant differences were found between the groups, regarding the duration of hospitalization, operative duration, and number of harvested lymph nodes, anastomotic leakage, postoperative ileus, bleeding, reoperation rates, mortality, and readmission rate at 30 days and bowel obstruction.

Hajibandeh et al. (2021) ^[23]	MA	UK	399	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The IA was associated with a significantly shorter incision length (MD -1.82, $p < 0.00001$), lower postoperative pain scores, on days 2,3,4 and 5 (MD -0.69, $p = 0.0007$; MD -0.80, $p = 0.02$; MD -0.83, $p = 0.01$; MD -0.49, $p < 0.00001$) and shorter duration of hospitalization (MD -0.27, $p = 0.03$), compared to EA.• no significant differences were observed between the two anastomoses techniques, regarding anastomotic leakage (RR 1.29, $p = 0.65$), postoperative morbidity (RR 0.79, $p = 0.47$), paralytic ileus (RR 0.60, $p = 0.45$), bleeding (RR 0.70, $p = 0.71$), SSI (RR 0.61, $p = 0.42$), number of harvested lymph nodes (MD 0.82, $p = 0.06$), conversion to open surgery (RD: -0.02, $p = 0.45$), and operative duration (MD 16.04, $p = 0.06$).
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Ferrer-Márquez et al. (2021) ^[24]	RCT	Spain	168	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 70% of patients had no post-operative complications and If complications presented post-operatively; paralytic ileus, surgical site infection and anastomotic leakage were the most common ones (20,63%, 10%, 6.25%, respectively), with either anastomoses types. • Surgical site infections were less commonly presented in the IA group compared to EA one (3.65% vs. 16.67%, P=0.008). • IA was associated with smaller incision length compared to EA (P=0.000) and with lower rates of post-operative pain compared to EA. • no significant differences were observed between the two anastomoses regarding the 7-day median post-operative duration.
Małczak et al. (2022) ^[25]	RCT	Poland	102	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The IA group had a shorter time to first flatus (32.8 hours) compared to EA (41.7 hrs), p = 0.017. • No significant differences were observed, between the two types of anastomoses, regarding time to first flatus, overall complications and operative duration.

Ishizuka et al. (2022) ^[26]	MA	Japan	3219	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rate of complication was higher in the EA group compared to the IA (22.6% vs 18.5%), which reached statistically significance (RR, 0.73; 95% CI: 0.57-0.95; P = 0.02; I2 = 57). • IA was associated with a lower rate of surgical site infections compared to EA (RR, 0.50; 95% CI: 0.34-0.71; P = 0.0002; I2 = 0%). • No significant differences were observed regarding the anastomotic leakage.
Seno et al. (2023) ^[27]	RCT	Italy	140	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The IA group had slightly higher costs when compared to the EA group, but the results were not statistically significant (7926.87 € vs. 7577.45 €; P = 0.704). • The IA group had a 608 euro extra intra-operative charge compared to EA (3058.84 € vs. 2450.15 €; P < 0.001). • There was a 542 euro extra charge per patient for the surgical equipment, in the IA group compared to the EA (1782.74 € vs. 1240.55 €; P < 0.001). • No significant differences were observed regarding the mean cost of operative room occupancy [1276.09 € vs. 1209.60 € (P = 0.405)], postoperative costs and outpatients costs, between the two approaches.

Table 3: Currently recruiting randomized clinical trials comparing the IA to EA

Title	Type of study	Aim	Design	Primary outcomes	Secondary outcomes
Intracorporeal Versus Extracorporeal Anastomosis In Laparoscopic Right Colon Resection Country: South Korea, Yonsei University Estimated date of completion: 2024 ID: NCT05077358 ^[28]	prospective, randomized, multi-center study	To compare intracorporeal versus extracorporeal anastomosis in performing laparoscopic right colectomy	241 patients Experimental group: IA Control group: EA	Surgical site infection within the first 30 postoperative days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 year disease free survival • Tissue morphometry within 30 postoperative days • Incision hernia at 1 year • Postoperative pain scores using the VAS within 7 postoperative days • Duration of hospitalization • Number of patient with Clavien-Dindo grade IIIb-IV at 30 days postoperatively • Operative duration • Conversion to open surgery
“Long-term Results in Intracorporeal Versus Extracorporeal Anastomosis in Laparoscopic Right Colectomy” Country: Spain, Fundació Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau Estimated date of completion: 2028 ID: NCT05446558 ^[29]	prospective, randomized, single-center study	To compare the IA to the EA in terms of long term outcomes and oncological outcomes	140 patients Experimental group: IA Control group: EA	Overall survival at 3 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disease free survival at 3 years • Local recurrence at 3 years • distant recurrence at 3 years • Incisional hernia at 3 years • Intestinal obstruction at 3 years • Costs of surgical material • Costs of operative room • Cost per global hospitalization • Costs per ICU hospitalization • Costs of tests during hospitalization

RESULTS

Operative duration

Measuring the operative duration is of vital importance, as it allows to account for staff scheduling, resource allocation, cost management and patient safety regarding exposure to anesthesia. Out of the twelve studies that examined the relationship between the anastomosing technique and the operative duration, four concluded that the IA was associated with higher operative duration. Particularly, Dohrn et al. (2022) found that the IA took four minutes longer compared to EA, in patients undergoing right colectomy with the robotic system. Similar result were observed by other researchers ^[10,14,21]. However eight studies found no statistically significant differences between the two approaches ^[11,15,16,18,19, 22,23,25].

Bowel function recovery

Bowel function recovery is a key aspect of a patient's recovery postoperatively. Monitoring and assessing bowel function recovery post-abdominal surgery can assist the healthcare providers to assess patients' progress and potentially identify complications early. The literature offers valuable insights regarding bowel function recovery, following IA or EA, including time to diet initiation and time to first stool/flatus. Overall, the IA appears to be associated with faster bowel function recovery, compared to EA ^[11,13,14,15,17,19, 21, 22, 25]. For example Bollo et al. (2022) ^[21] concluded that the IA was associated with faster bowel function recovery, by one day. However, as with operative time, discrepancies are evident as three studies found no significant differences between the two approaches on bowel function recovery ^[8,12,18].

Duration of hospitalization

Duration of hospitalization is an important aspect to measure in any surgical specialty as will allow to account for resource allocation, costs management, patients safety (hospital acquired infections, deep vein thrombosis, etc.) and patient satisfaction. Overall, six studies showed that the IA was associated with shorter hospital stay, compared to EA ^[11,13,15,16,19,23]. For instance, Ricci et al. (2017) ^[16] concluded that IA could decrease hospitalization approximately by a day. However, six studies found no statistically significant results ^[8,10,14,18,22,25].

Anastomotic leakage

Anastomotic leakage is a major complication that could arise following any type of colectomy. Ferrer-Marquez et al. (2021) ^[24], observed that it was the third most commonly presented complication following colectomy and was seen in 6.25% of patient undergoing the procedure irrespective of the anastomoses type. Interestingly, even though the IA approach is more technically demanding, there was no significant association observed between the IA and anastomotic leakage compared to EA ^[11-13, 15, 16, 19, 22-24, 26].

Ileus

Another major complication of abdominal surgery is postoperative ileus (POI). Ileus can arise in 20.63% of patients undergoing colectomy irrespective of the anastomosing technique^[24]. Thus measuring POI is very important as it can assist healthcare providers to identify procedures associated with POI and act in accordance with the patients' needs. Bollo et al. (2022)^[21] concluded that IA was associated with lower rate of POI compared to EA (13% vs 30%, respectively). However, six studies found no significant association between the type of anastomoses and the rate of POI^[11, 14, 15, 19, 22, 23].

Incision length

Measuring the incision length can be vital for reasons such as cosmetic outcomes, healing and recovery and risk of infections. In total, six studies agree that the IA approach led to smaller incision length^[15,16, 21-24]. Particularly, Bollo et al. (2022)^[21] concluded that opting for the IA approach led to a 1cm smaller incision compared to EA. On the other hand, three studies showed no statistically significant relationship between the anastomoses and the incision length^[10, 11, 18].

Morbidity and Mortality

Measuring morbidity and mortality is of utmost importance when comparing surgical approaches and techniques, not only for patient safety and quality assurance, but also for legal and ethical reasons. Regarding the IA, no significant associations were observed regarding morbidity^[13,18, 23] and mortality^[11, 12, 15, 16, 19, 22]. It should be noted, however, that Cirocchi et al. (2013)^[12] could not determine the post-operative morbidity due to high heterogeneity.

Blood loss

Blood loss is an important aspect as it is related to patient safety, postoperative care and related complications. Overall two studies concluded that the IA was significantly associated with lower blood loss compared to EA. Particularly, Bollo et al. (2022)^[21] showed that the blood loss of IA was 3% and EA was 14%. On the contrary, seven studies found no statistically significant association between the anastomoses type and blood loss^[10, 11, 15, 16, 19, 22, 23].

Post-operative pain and analgesia use

Measuring post-operative pain and analgesia use post-surgery is important as it can negatively affect patients' return to activities and the duration of hospitalization. The IA was associated with lower postoperative pain compared to the EA. For instance, Zhang et al. (2021)^[22] observed that patients reported lower pain on the 3rd, 4th and 5th

postoperative days, whilst using the visual analog scale, compared to EA. Similar results were reported by similar studies, like Hajibandeh et al. (2021)^[23] who reported lower pain, for the 2nd to the 5th postoperative days, in patients who underwent IA compared to EA^[21,23,24]. Regarding postoperative analgesia, two studies showed that IA was related to lower postoperative use, compared to EA^[11,21]. However, one study found no significant differences^[16].

Wound and surgical site infections

Measuring and monitoring SSIs and wound infections, is an essential component for patient safety, decreasing antibiotic usage and duration of hospitalization. In total, five studies showed that IA decreases the rate of wound and SSIs, compared to EA^[16,19,22,24,26]. Particularly, Ricci et al. (2017)^[16] concluded that the rate of wound infections and/or surgical site infections was 4.9% for IA versus (vs) 8.9% for EA. In contrast, three studies found no statistical significance between the anastomoses type and the infection rate^[10,11,15].

Herniation

Ricci et al. (2017)^[16] observed that the rate of incisional hernia was lower for IA compared to EA (2.3% vs 13.7%, for IA and EA, respectively), but found no significant differences regarding internal hernia. Lastly, two studies found no statistical significant results between the anastomoses type and the rate of herniation^[10,15].

Other parameters

Adequate intestinal perfusion is a cornerstone of a viable anastomosis. Dohrn et al. (2022)^[9] examined the relationship and found that IA was associated with better perfusion compared to EA. Similarly, measuring physiological and biochemical markers is important as they provide insights into the surgical stress a patient has been exposed to. Mari et al. (2018)^[17] observed that patients who underwent IA had lower levels of IL-6 and CRP on the 1st, 3rd and the 5th postoperative days. Moreover, no significant differences were observed regarding IA vs EA in terms of time to ambulation, nausea^[1], nasogastric tube-re-insertion^[11], re-admission rate^[11,18,19,22], re-operation rate^[16,18,19,22] conversion to open surgery^[15,16,23], number of harvested lymph nodes^[11,15,16,18,22,23], and bowel obstruction^[22]. Regarding costs, Seno et al. (2023)^[27] observed that patients who underwent IA had statistically significantly higher intraoperative costs, by 608 euros, compared to EA. However, there was not a significant association regarding the total costs between the two types of anastomoses. Furthermore, Selvy et al. (2020)^[20] concluded that IA was associated with a 50% lower rate of parietal abscess formation compared to EA, whereas Wu et al. (2017)^[15], found no significant association between the anastomosing approach and the intra-abdominal abscess formation.

DISCUSSION

Research gaps and future directions

Even though some trends become evident when comparing the IA to the EA, some outcomes are either underreported or examined in a fewer studies compared to other ones. For instance, majority of the studies place emphasis on short term outcomes, like duration of hospitalization, operative duration and immediate operative and post-operative complications, such as ileus and blood loss. Long term outcomes including quality of life, long term recurrence and readmission rates and long term morbidity and mortality are not discussed extensively and need to be further investigated in the future, in order to determine which type of anastomoses is optimal. Moreover, patient centered outcomes and patient satisfaction are also under-examined. Patient centered outcomes may often contain biases as they are self-reported via questionnaires. However, when opting for a surgical approach a more holistic view should be taken into account by healthcare and health policy professionals. Following up on patients who have had the procedure, in an organized fashion, can assist in gaining the patients' perspective on the approach. Seno et al. (2023)^[27] has analyzed the difference in costs regarding the two types of anastomoses. However, more studies are required to validate the conclusions. In addition, cost-benefit analysis should include, not only the immediate costs, but also the broader financial implication of the type of anastomosis, including patient financial burden, national healthcare system burden and long-term healthcare costs. Subgroup analysis of the data is also lacking in the literature. The results can be stratified by patient demographic, age, cancer stage and sex. Lastly, the emotional and psychological impact of the approaches has not been reported so far. Future studies should possibly include it via a patient questionnaire.

Currently, there are two randomized clinical trials recruiting, which aim to compare the IA to the EA. The clinical trial by Yonsei University^[28] is of a particular importance. The study examines the short term outcomes, like SSI within 30-postoperative days, but also the long term outcomes, which are currently underreported, such as 3-years disease free survival. However, the study falls short in exploring patients centered outcomes, like patient satisfaction, return to activity and quality of life post-surgery. Moreover, the study does not have a large enough sample size and by extent long follow up duration may be a challenge. The study by Fundació Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau^[29], is of an interest as it focuses on long term outcomes. Particularly, local recurrence, disease free survival, distant recurrence, incisional hernia and intestinal obstruction, will be measured at three years postoperatively, addressing the need for examining long term outcomes currently underreported in the literature. In addition, the study will perform an in depth economic analysis, including the costs related to surgical instruments and materials, hospitalization, total costs and intensive care unit costs, providing a holistic view on both hospitals' and patients' financial burden. Despite addressing crucial factors underreported in the literature, the study has a small sample size (140 patients), which could further decrease if patients are not properly followed up. Also, as with Yonsei University, patient centered outcomes are still unexplored.

RCTs are essential for advancing surgical knowledge, improve quality of healthcare and ensuring patient safety. Also, they can minimize biases and allow researchers to draw conclusions in controlled environments. Future RCTs comparing the IA to the EA could potentially investigate both long and short term outcomes. For instance a RCT could examine, the recurrence and readmission rates at 5 years. It could also examine the quality of life post-operatively, using validated tools as well as the 5-year morbidity and mortality. Moreover, subgroup analysis can add value to the literature by specifically examining how different patient characteristics, i.e. sex, cancer stage, age, etc., may influence the results of the type of anastomoses. Also, patient satisfaction and quality of life within the subgroup can be examined. Furthermore RCTs are also needed to assess the emotional and psychological impact wellbeing of patients immediate pre- post- and 2- years post-surgery. This can assist physicians in identifying procedures that are less likely to negatively impact the psychological wellbeing of the patient and establish rapport with their patients.

Implications on healthcare professionals

Healthcare professionals and particularly surgeons need to consider the available evidence when deciding on IA vs EA. Even though, the overall trend favors the IA over the EA, there is still conflicting evidence. Surgeons need to take into account various factors, including specific surgical goals, patient and cancer characteristics, patient preferences and their own skillset. In addition, this review underlines, amongst others, the importance of patient centered care. Quality of life and patient satisfaction is of utmost importance and is currently completely overlooked. Surgeons need to openly communicate with patients and understand their preferences and set surgical expectations. As the long term outcomes are underreported, surgeons should consider the potential impact that the anastomoses technique could have on long term morbidity. Lastly, physicians involved in surgical planning should take into consideration the costs' implications and resource allocation. While some studies indicate a shorter duration of hospitalization and no significant differences in costs, the overall economic impact may vary among centers and patients.

Implications on policy makers

Guidelines should take into account the current evidence on IA and EA for the treatment of right side CRC, in minimally invasive surgery. They should be updated often and incorporate the updated evidence. This can assist in standardizing care among hospitals and improving patient outcomes. Moreover, the research gaps identified in this review need to be addressed. Policy makers should provide funds in research to assess the long term outcomes, patient centered outcomes, and patient satisfaction and perform subgroup analyses to understand which patient subgroups benefit most from each type of anastomoses. In addition, policy makers should promote initiatives for the collection of standardized data on patient satisfaction, economic factors and surgical outcomes related to IA and EA. This can assist in monitoring and continuously improving the quality

of care provided by the surgeons. Furthermore, policy maker should take into account the cost difference between the two types of anastomosis and allocate resources accordingly and in a well fashioned manner. Lastly, they need to take into account the regulatory aspects associated with colectomies. This may include that the evidence based approaches align with the patients' needs and adopting and monitoring newer approaches.

Strengths and limitations

This review offers a comprehensive coverage of the outcomes between the IA and the EA. It analyses a variety of variables, from short to long term and oncological outcomes as well as the efficiency of each procedure like the duration of hospitalization and the operative duration. Moreover, it includes articles published within the past decade, offering an updated review of each outcome. Multiple studies have been included in the review, like SR/MA and RCTs, offering a holistic view from high evidence level papers. This variety assists in minimizing biases associated with each type of study. The research also identified research gaps and provides future RCTs currently recruiting as well as providing potential RCTs can you bridge the gaps. Lastly, it also discusses the implications of the findings for policy makers and healthcare professionals, offering a different perspective compared to other literature reviews.

However, this review also has its limitations. The review does not discuss the risk of bias in the included studies. Assessing the quality of the studies and being on the lookout for biases is essential in determining the reliability and validity of the findings. Also, heterogeneity is a problem, as some studies mention high levels of heterogeneity. This can affect the ability to draw meaningful conclusions from the data. Publication bias, also, has not been assessed in the present studies. This can potential skew the overall trends. Lastly, majority of the reviews included, have a small sample size without subgroup analysis, which could limit the statistical power and generalizability of the results.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, the IA was associated with faster bowel function recovery, smaller incision length, shorter duration of hospitalization, lower blood loss, lower postoperative pain and analgesia usage, lower rates of wound and surgical site infections, herniation rates, better intestinal perfusion, lower levels of postoperative inflammation markers and reduced rate of parietal abscess, compared to EA. No significant differences were observed regarding the anastomotic leakage, ileus, morbidity and mortality, time to ambulation, nausea, nasogastric tube re-insertion, re-admission rate, re-operation rate, conversion to open surgery, number of harvested lymph nodes and bowel obstruction, between the two types of anastomoses. However, the intracorporeal approach required longer operative duration compared to extracorporeal. In addition, conflicting evidence was present in the review and several research gaps were identified. Particularly, long term outcomes, patient centered outcomes, patient satisfaction, and subgroup analysis, in depth cost-

benefit analysis, and the psychological and emotional impact on the patient, were underreported and this necessitates further research via RCTs. lastly, healthcare professionals and policy makers should understand the benefits of each anastomosing techniques and effectively communicate with the patients regarding the procedure.

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